

Definitive proof that CO₂ does not cause global warming

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Abstract

As shown by a comparison of NASA/GMAO re-analysis images of atmospheric SO₂ aerosol pollution, the 2023 El Nino, which began around March-April, was caused by a large decrease in the amount of global SO₂ aerosols in our atmosphere.

This decrease was primarily due to Net-Zero activities banning the burning of fossil fuels (which also produces SO₂ aerosols), reduced industrial activity because of high energy costs, the closing of coal-fired power plants, increased use of electric vehicles, mandated lower sulfur in shipping fuels, etc.

Keywords: Climate Change; SO₂ aerosols; SO₂ Chem Maps; El Ninos

1. Introduction

Volcanic eruptions with an explosivity index of VEI4, or more, if not erupting during an El Nino, normally cause about 0.2 Deg of cooling, because of their injection of sulfurous compounds into the stratosphere. There, they are quickly converted to the Sulfur Dioxide (SO₂) aerosol (fine droplets of Sulfuric Acid). These droplets are reflective, and cool the Earth by reducing the amount of the incoming solar radiation that reaches its surface [1].

Industrial SO₂ aerosols have the same cooling effect [1], and when their concentration in the atmosphere is reduced, such as due to global “Clean Air” efforts, decreased industrial activity, Net-Zero efforts banning the burning of fossil fuels (which also produces SO₂ aerosol emissions), etc., an El Nino usually forms because of the cleaner, more transparent air [2].

NASA/GMAO produces global and regional re-analysis “Chem Maps” of various atmospheric pollutants, including SO₂, and it was wondered whether they would show the expected global decrease in SO₂ aerosol emissions causing the 2023 El Nino.

2. Method

“Chem Maps” for May 31, 2023, Feb 20, 2022, and Jan 1, 2020 were downloaded and used for comparison, as shown below

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Figure 1 Chem Map for May 31, 2023

Figure 2 Chem Map for Feb. 2, 2022

This image for Feb 2, 2022 shows more SO₂ in the atmosphere than in 2023, and the following image for Jan 1, 2020, shows even more, showing that global SO₂ aerosol levels have been on a decreasing trend.

Figure 3 Chem Map for Jan 1, 2020

3. Discussion

Current thinking maintains that our warming climate is due to increasing levels of CO₂ in the atmosphere, but the above images prove that the warming is actually due to decreasing levels of SO₂ aerosols in the atmosphere. The NASA/GMAO images are archived back to 1980, so that earlier warming periods, such as 1997-98, and 2014-16, can be visited to show that the warming of those periods was also due to decreased levels of atmospheric SO₂ aerosols [3].

4. Conclusion

The Trillions of dollars now being spent annually to reduce CO₂ levels are a complete waste of resources, and will have the unexpected effect of causing global temperatures to rise to those of The Medieval Warm Period (MWP) (circa 950-1250), or higher (~ 1.5-2.0 Deg. C warmer than now), because of our much larger population and industrial energy inputs.

In light of the above, it is essential that ALL activities that remove SO₂ aerosols from our atmosphere, such as Net-Zero, be halted, so as to limit the amount of warming that will occur, if not already too late.

References

- [1] GOOGLE "Atmospheric Aerosols: What are they, and why are they so important?"
- [2] The Definitive Cause of La Nina and El Nino Events <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.1.0124>
- [3] <https://Fluid.nccs.nasa.gov/weather> Select "Chem Maps', Global, Total Column, and SO₂.